

Forecast of SO₂ Air Contamination Utilizing Artificial Neural Network: Sample of City Meerut

¹Lokesh Kumar, ²Gaurav Kumar, ³Dushyant Kumar

^{1,2} Department of Mathematics, NAS College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

³ Galgotias College of Engineering and Technology, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

Corresponding Author: Lokesh Kumar, Department of Mathematics, NAS College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh 250003, India.

Abstract-- SO₂ is among the air poisons that assume the best part in air contamination. In this study, using data from 2019 to 2023, estimates of how this contaminant was affecting human health and the environment were made using artificial neural networks, a well-liked learning method in use today. Information having a place with Meerut territory, where the center of industry is located, was acquired by the Air Observation Center of Uttar Pradesh Pollution Control Board (UPPCB), and modeling and optimization were completed in SPSS programming. The obtained SO₂ estimation results were subjected to a multilayer perceptron analysis before being compared with the actual data. Furthermore, the SO₂ value for the province of Meerut has been recorded to occasionally beyond the permissible level, particularly during periods of high production.

Index Terms: SO₂, Air Pollution, Artificial Neural Network (ANN).

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and particulate matter (PM₁₀) are on the rise as industrialization continues (Kumar, 2018). Because of the adverse consequences of this increment on human well-being and nature, it makes extraordinary harm the public economies. In this manner, these air toxins are firmly checked, and local and general state run administrations take steps appropriately. Among these toxins, SO₂ is the poison that assume a significant part in the evaluation of well-being and ecological effects (Boznar, 1993).

Sulfur dioxide (SO₂) is an exceptionally perilous air toxin for human well-being, which essentially influences respiratory capabilities (Chelani et al, 2002). Through its transformation into sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) and sulfate, it has the potential to pose an indirect threat to human health (Reshma, 2020). Both man-made and natural sources produce sulfur dioxide. Volcanoes structure the beginning of the vitally normal asset. One of the most important human-caused sources is the combustion of petroleum products, especially coal and diesel. The main producers of SO₂ are power plants, industries that handle and process metals, and automobiles that operate on these fuels.

In our nation as well as around the world, these indicators are periodically measured and meticulously examined. These toxins are monitored in Meerut by the UPPCB's air observation facilities. Materials and gases that affect air quality are measured in these stations. The results are periodically posted on the center's website.

In this review, it is planned to examine what is happening of SO₂ poison in Meerut area of Uttar Pradesh, where the center of industry is located, and to demonstrate and foresee with multilayer perceptron technique. In this context, SO₂ information between the years 2019-2023, acquired from the UPPCB, was examined. Then, the information between 2019-2023 was displayed in SPSS programming and forecasts were gotten. In this process, multilayer perceptron method was utilized.

II. METHODOLOGY

An ANN is a computational or numerical model that draws motivation from the engineering and usefulness of biological brain network. By and large, their neuronal activation approach, preparing approach, network structure, association example, and information handling ability characterize them. The most widely used neural network model is known as Multilayer Perceptron. Since this type of neural network needs an ideal output to learn, it is alluded to as a regulated network. Utilizing verifiable information, the goal of this sort of network is to construct a model that precisely interfaces the input and output. As such, in the event that the ideal result is obscure, the model can be used to deliver the output. At the point when the sources of info are moved from the input layer to hidden layer, they are increased by the interconnection weights. They are added together and

afterward took care of by a nonlinear function (frequently the hyperbolic tangent) inside the hidden layer. On the off chance that there are many hidden layers, the handled information is expanded by the association weights again when it leaves the primary hidden layer, added, and afterward managed by the second hidden layer, etc.

The result of the neural network is finally delivered by duplicating the information by the availability weights and handling it once again in the output layer. A number of input-output mapping experiments are required to train the neural network for any task. These are the most crucial pieces of information for any trained neural network to have in order to produce reliable results. Thus, to incorporate all the important data, the training sample information should be genuinely huge and contain a large number of information from different process parameters and trial settings.

III. TIME SERIES STUDY

Multilayer perceptron is used to complete the time series analysis, and its definition is as follows:

$$A_{q+1} = f(A_q, A_{q-1}, \dots, A_1)$$

Here the inputs are $A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots, A_q$ and output is A_{q+1} .

The type of f above is created using multilayer perceptron.

The fifth data point is named the output, though the initial four are viewed as the inputs.

3.1 Analysing Data

The UPPCB assembles information for its site relating to the state's several metropolitan districts by screening data on three components of air contamination: SO₂, PM₁₀ and NO₂. At the Meerut city's Kesharganj street, SO₂ levels are assessed. The level has been crucial throughout the previous few years. The city of Meerut's air quality would likewise decay with an expansion in SO₂ contamination. For Kesharganj street in Meerut, SO₂ information from January 2019 to June 2023 has been gathered for examination. Summary of the information is displayed in figure 1:

Figure 1. Actual data of SO₂

3.2 Analysis of ANN

Utilizing SPSS programming, we have made a multilayer perceptron model for the city of Meerut. In total, 51 information points are used in this study. There are 47 groupings made from these important pieces of information. Each group has five data points. The fifth SO₂ information point was taken as the result, while the initial four were utilized as the input. Once more, Dismissing the first data point, the following four data points are inputs and next in series is output. While S_{Output} is the assignment for the output data point, S_A, S_B, S_C and S_D are the underlying four data inputs. The time series model that is displayed below has been made.

Table 1 shows network information having input, hidden and output layers and tells us about covariates, activation function in hidden and output layers. In Table 2 model summary is given where we get that relative error in training is 0.518 and in testing is 0.341. Table 3 has parameter estimates and Table 4 tells us about importance of independent variables. Figure 2 has information regarding structure of the network. Figure 3 depicts predicted values against Output. Figure 4 has the information regarding predicted values against residuals. Figure 5 shows normalized importance of independent variables in the network.

Table 1
Network Data

Input Layer	Covariates	1	S_A
		2	S_B
		3	S_C
		4	S_D
	Number of Units ^a	4	
	Technique for Rescaling Covariates	Standardized	
Hidden Layer(s)	Number of Hidden Layers		1
	Units in Hidden Layer 1 ^a		3
	Activation Function		Hyperbolic tangent
Output Layer	Dependent Variables	1	S_Output
	Number of Units		1
	Technique for Rescaling Scale Dependents		Standardized
	Activation Function		Identity
	Error Function		Sum of Squares

a. Excluding the bias unit

Figure 2

Table 2

Model Summary

Training	Sum of Squares Error	9.068
	Relative Error	.518
	Stopping Rule Used	1 successive step(s) without a reduction in error
	Training Time	0:00:00.01
Testing	Sum of Squares Error	.880
	Relative Error	.341

Dependent Variable: S_Output

a. The testing sample is the foundation for error calculations.

Table 3
Parameter Estimates

Predictor		Predicted			
		Hidden Layer 1			Output Layer
		H(1:1)	H(1:2)	H(1:3)	S Output
Input Layer	(Bias)	-.371	.038	.360	
	S_A	-.069	1.518	-.557	
	S_B	.329	.429	-.828	
	S_C	-.181	.504	-.018	
	S_D	-.051	.454	.870	
Hidden Layer 1	(Bias)				-.046
	H(1:1)				.045
	H(1:2)				.873
	H(1:3)				.793

Figure 3

Figure 4

Table 4

Importance of Independent Variable		
	Importance	Normalized Importance
S_A	.196	44.4%
S_B	.189	42.8%
S_C	.175	39.7%
S_D	.441	100.0%

Figure 5

IV. CONCLUSION

Time series investigation is utilized to figure the SO₂ values for Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India. The model displays non-linearity. An ANN model is created to handle non-linearity. Multilayer perceptron is used to create the time series model. The model shows that there is relative error of 0.518 in training and relative error of 0.341 in testing. This demonstrates that future SO₂ levels might be predicted from past values.

REFERENCES

1. **Bhavsar R. (2019)** “Air Pollution Monitoring Using Artificial Neural Network”, *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 10 (12), pp. 515-519
2. **Boznar M., Lesjak M., and Mlakar P. (1993)** “A neural network-based method for short-term predictions of ambient So₂ concentrations in highly polluted industrial areas of complex terrain”, *Atmospheric Environment*, 27B, pp. 221-230
3. **Boznar M.Z. and Mlakar P. (2002)** “Use of neural networks in the field of air pollution modeling”, *Air Pollution Modeling and Its Application XV*, pp. 375-383
4. **Chelani A.B., Raoi C.V., Phadke K.M. and Hasan M.Z. (2002)** “Prediction of sulfur dioxide concentration using artificial neural networks”, *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 17, pp. 161-168
5. **Cogliani E. (2001)** “Air pollution forecast in cities by an air pollution index highly correlated with meteorological variables”, *Atmospheric Environment*, 35, pp. 2871- 2877
6. **Freeman A. M. III,** “Air pollution and property values, a further comment”, *Review of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 56, pp. 554– 556, Nov. 1974
7. **Gardner M.W. and Dorling S.R. (1999)** “Neural network modelling and prediction of hourly NO_x and NO₂ concentrations in urban air in London”, *Atmospheric Environment*, 33, pp. 709-719
8. **Guo C., Liu G. and Chen C.H. (2020)** “Air Pollution Concentration Forecast Method Based on the Deep Ensemble Neural Network”, *Hindawi Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, Vol. 2020, Article ID 8854649, 13 pages
9. **Jef H., Clemens M., Gerwin D., Frans F. and Olivier B. (2005)** “A neural network forecast for daily average PM₁₀ concentrations in Belgium” *Atmospheric Environment*, 39, pp. 3279-3289
10. **Kumar G., Sharma R.K. (2017)** “Air Pollution Evaluation Methods”, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Development*, 13 (9), pp. 12-17
11. **Kumar G. (2018)** “Time series analysis of PM₁₀ for Bulandshahr Industrial Area in NCR using Multiple Linear Regression”, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Development*, 14 (3), pp. 56-62
12. **Kumar G. (2018)** “Time series analysis of PM₁₀ for Noida Sector 1 Industrial Area in NCR using Multiple Linear Regression”, *Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, Section E-Math. & Stat.*, 37 (2), pp. 273-277
13. **Nagendra S.M.S. and Khare M. (2005)** “Modelling urban air quality using artificial neural network”, *Clean Technologies and Environment Policy*, 7, pp. 116–126
14. **Niharika, Venkatadri M. and Rao P. S. (2014)** “A survey on Air Quality forecasting Techniques”, *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, 5 (1), pp. 103-107
15. **Nunnari G., Dorling S., Schlink U., Cawley G., Foxall R. and Chatterton T. (2004)** “Modelling SO₂ concentration at a point with statistical approaches”, *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 19, pp. 887-905
16. **Prachi, Kumar N. and Matta G. (2011)** “Artificial neural network applications in air quality monitoring and management”, *International Journal for Environmental Rehabilitation and Conservation*, 2(1), pp. 30 – 64
17. **Reshma J. (2020)** “Analysis and Prediction of Air Quality”, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 7 (1), pp. 266-270

18. **Zaefizadeh M., Khayatnezhad M. and Gholamin R. (2011)** “Comparison of Multiple Linear Regressions (MLR) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) in Predicting the Yield Using its Components in the Hulless Barley”, *American-Eurasian Journal of Agricultural & Environmental Sciences*, 10 (1), pp. 60-64
19. **SPSS27 software**, SPSS Inc., <http://www.spss.com>.